

LIFE SATISFACTION AMONG RESIDENTS OF SLOVAK-UKRAINIAN BORDERLANDS

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The aim of the research was to assess how satisfied the residents of border regions are with significant areas of their lives. In a study comparing life satisfaction among residents living in the western part of Ukraine (N = 267) and residents of eastern Slovakia (N = 245), individual characteristics, self-efficacy, and positive affect were interpreted in accordance with the homeostatically protected mood hypothesis. Life satisfaction was assessed using an index, a hybrid reflective-formative construct aggregating four significant areas of life. The effect of commonly surveyed demographic characteristics was controlled while the influence of two personal characteristics was tested: general self-efficacy as a direct factor and positive affect as a moderator of life satisfaction. The results indicate higher level of life satisfaction among Ukrainian residents, with the moderator effect being insignificant.

Key words: index; life satisfaction; Slovakia; Ukraine; borderlands; HPMood; PLS-SEM.

1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of this work was to assess the subjective reality of people living in a specific geographical area as well as to analyse personal characteristics as probable factors of life satisfaction. Existing composite indices were not suitable for this purpose (see Land and Michalos 2018, for five examples), as they are oriented towards assessing well-being in a broad sense, or subjective well-being, which is an abstract assessment of one's own satisfaction or happiness based on a positive and abstract view of oneself. As a result, the path of constructing an original life satisfaction index was chosen for the purposes of the research project,

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in which the concept of life satisfaction was defined as a subjective assessment of objective living conditions. Given that the assessed living conditions represented four significant areas of life, aggregated into an overall score, a hybrid reflective-formative measurement model was chosen for the construct measured in this way (further details in the methodology). The structure of this article is as follows: second section presents the theoretical background and proposed research model. Section 2.1 briefly characterizes the living conditions of the inhabitants in two self-governing regions in Slovakia bordering Ukraine as well as the inhabitants of the Transcarpathian region of Ukraine. Section 2.2 defines life satisfaction as a hybrid reflective-formative construct, section 2.3 defines personal characteristics – self-efficacy and positive affect as presumed factors of life satisfaction and section 2.4 presents the proposed research model. Third section covers methodology, fourth the results and final section the discussion and conclusion.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND PROPOSED RESEARCH MODEL

2.1 The living conditions of the inhabitants in two self-governing regions in Slovakia bordering Ukraine as well as the inhabitants of the Transcarpathian region of Ukraine

Economic conditions in both countries. While Ukraine has long been among the lower middle-income countries, reaching the upper middle-income category in 2023, Slovakia has been among high-income countries for over a decade (World Bank 2025). In saying that, the Prešov and Košice self-governing regions in Slovakia and the Transcarpathian region in Ukraine produced GDP per capita below the national average in their respective countries (i.e. the Prešov region reaches around 60% of Slovak per capita GDP, the Košice region around 80% and the Transcarpathian region around 33% of Ukrainian per capita GDP). Their development potential largely depends on the nature of the border and the conditions for mutual trade and cross-border cooperation as they can draw productive advantages and economic development opportunities from their mutual proximity and connections. Within the past decade, both the Prešov and Košice regions reported continuous growth, while the regional economy of Transcarpathia has experienced severe shrinkage since 2014. It still lags significantly behind the performance of regional economies in eastern Slovakia, reaching around 10-15% of regional per capita GDP in Prešov or Košice regions (CESCI 2020; Brenzovych, Lačný and Tsalan 2023). In addition, unemployment persistently exceeds national averages (3-5 percentage points above the national average for both eastern Slovak regions and 1-3 percentage points above the national average for the Transcarpathian region in Ukraine) and contributes to the relatively low level of purchasing power in these regions. The lack of cross-border transport connectivity and long waiting times at border crossings have not been conducive to collaborations requiring physical contact, including labour market commuting, small cross-border trade and face-to-face meetings. The obstacles related to cross-border economic relations are still hindering factors regarding foreign investment, trade relations, value chains, supplier networks and business development (CESCI 2020; Duleba, Lendel and Oravcová 2023).

Environmental conditions in both countries. Among the most significant environmental issues in both the Slovak and Ukrainian border regions, is the need to complete adequate environment protection and eliminate the negative environmental cross-border impacts resulting from the different environmental infrastructure of both counties. This is especially with regards to waste

management infrastructure. The recycling rate is much higher in the EU-28 than in both Slovak border regions (where it counts for up to 40%), while its extent is negligible in Transcarpathia. Another issue is wastewater treatment which is unresolved in many Ukrainian settlements. Although the level of greenhouse gas emissions has decreased, these regions have been able to show little progress in terms of joint energy management, efficiency and renewable energy resources (CESCI 2020; Brenzovych et al. 2023).

Local governments in both countries. In terms of local government in Ukraine and Slovakia, the fundamental difference is in the lower flexibility and degree of autonomy of Ukrainian local and regional governments. The administrative-territorial structure and distribution of powers between the different levels of government in Ukraine still bears a strong centralisation as a legacy of the Soviet past. The system comprises four levels (centre, oblasts, raions and municipalities) with no clear delineation of responsibilities and powers between them. A very fragmented settlement structure with thousands of municipal councils without sufficient resources for service delivery and project implementation remains a persistent problem. On the other hand, the fundamental decentralisation of public administration in Slovakia has already taken place in 1998–2005. A significant set of competences, assets and liabilities has been transferred from central institutions to self-governing regions, municipalities and towns. Within the scope of its competences, a self-governing region may cooperate with territorial and administrative units or with authorities of other states performing regional functions. It has the right to become a member of an international association of territorial units or territorial authorities (Cirner 2023). Recently, there has been low trust displayed in private and public entities operating at the local level across all population groups in Ukraine. Indeed, 47% of respondents reported having very little or no trust in local authorities (IOM 2025). According to the OECD survey on drivers of trust in public institutions for 2024, around 40% of respondents in Slovakia had trust in the regional and local government (OECD 2024). Residents' satisfaction with the work and services of local government in border regions is linked especially to their bottom-up response during crisis situations (Ručinská, Fečko, Mital' and Jesenko 2023), cross-border public services (Mariančíková and Király 2022; Toplak Petrovič and Tomažič 2023) and their impact on transition processes and Europeanization (Reiners 2025).

2.2 Life satisfaction as a hybrid reflective-formative construct

The term “life satisfaction” is often used as part of three frequently used terms: quality of life, well-being and happiness. These are sometimes understood interchangeably. Glatzer, Camfield, Møller and Rojas (2015, 2) have noted that “The mixture of terms was introduced at the beginning of this research direction in the US. One of the first main studies spoke of ‘Quality of Life’ (Campbell et al. 1976) and the other of ‘Wellbeing’ and ‘Life quality’ (Andrews and Withey 1976); ‘Wellbeing’ was used later by Campbell (1981).” As far as life satisfaction and happiness are concerned, conceptual and semantic connections can be identified. According to Veenhoven (2015, 222): “The view that we ‘calculate’ happiness from the plusses and minuses of life fits the cognitive component I called ‘contentment’. The view that life-satisfaction is inferred from how we feel most of the time fits the affective component, which I called ‘hedonic level of affect’.” In addition to these three terms, another term used in research is “subjective wellbeing” which also includes life satisfaction. Easterlin (2015, 283) has stated that “the term ‘subjective wellbeing’ encompasses a variety of measures of feelings of wellbeing – happiness, life satisfaction, ladder-of-life –which are treated here as interchangeable.”

The focus of this analysis is not conceptual but factual. In other words, it aims to find out how satisfied individuals are with their lives, what their subjectively assessed life reality looks like in a specific geographical area, and how their personal characteristics relate to their satisfaction. This focus corresponds to that posed by Land and Michalos (2018, 859) who "...measure psychological satisfaction, happiness, and life fulfilment by using survey research instruments that ascertain the subjective reality in which people live." To assess the well-being of the population in a broader sense, tools are used that cover a wide range of areas integrating material living conditions and quality of life. The OECD assesses 11 different areas ranging from health to subjective well-being and work-life balance. There are important tools with a very broad understanding of well-being such as The Canadian Index of Well-Being (CIW), where "...a broad understanding of well-being, regarded by its developers as roughly synonymous with 'overall quality of life.'" (Land and Michalos 2018, 856). This broad conceptualization includes eight equally weighted domains, ranging from living standards and democratic engagement to the environment.

While approaches to quality of life and subjective wellbeing, which also includes life satisfaction, use scales that assume a reflective measurement model for their assessment, our work assumes that how satisfied individuals are with their lives, what their subjectively assessed life reality looks like, should be determined using an index. In both cases, the constructs surveyed represent the sum of the scores of responses to the items on the scale or index, but there are two different approaches to justifying the combination of responses to individual questionnaire items into an overall score. These are based on conceptually different assumptions: (a) when items share a common cause and (b) when items share a common consequence. If several items originate from the same underlying cause, they reflect the variable that drives them. Conversely, if they lead to a shared consequence, they collectively define or constitute the aggregate variable (DeVellis and Thorpe 2021, 183). The first approach usually uses the term scale, while the second uses the term index. In the case of the index, two alternatives are used. The first is a formative composite index, which consists of a list of items that do not have conceptual unity, while the second is a formative causal index, which contains items conceptually linked by theory. The current study is based on the idea that the satisfaction of residents living in the Slovak-Ukrainian borderlands is a concept composed of several specific areas of satisfaction. It is therefore a summary of various specific satisfactions that can be aggregated into an overall score using a formative causal index. The items that make up the index are not interchangeable, unlike scales in which responses are the product of a single latent variable and responses have a common cause. In other words, if a person evaluates their satisfaction with their life in general or in one specific area of life, then it is very likely that their answers will represent one common factor, a common cause for evaluation. If a person expresses their subjective assessment of different areas of their life in which they currently live or have lived for a long time, then the assessments may be relatively independent depending on which areas of assessment were selected for the questionnaire. The items in the index that represent different areas relate to different things and are therefore not interchangeable. When considering an instrument where each domain is represented by only one item, changing any item would change the aggregate variable, while the other items would remain unaffected. If individual specific domains consist of multiple items, they may have scale properties, while the combination of different domains into an overall score may have index properties. In this case, it is a higher-order construct (HOC) whose domains are reflexive in nature, and the overall score is formative in nature. It is therefore a hybrid measurement with a reflexive-formative nature.

2.3 Personal characteristics – self-efficacy and positive affect as factors of life satisfaction

Land and Michalos (2018) have noted five insufficiently researched factors with regards to life satisfaction. The first is failing to look at human activity. As has been pointed out, many studies repeatedly rely on demographic characteristics such as age, income, gender, ethnicity, or race as the main explanatory or predictive variables, even though their explanatory power tends to be relatively limited. They add that it is impossible to gain a reliable understanding of people's quality of life without knowing how individuals think and feel. As such, the current study examined what residents living in regions on both sides of the Slovak-Ukrainian border think and feel by looking at two variables: what they thought about themselves in terms of their own self-efficacy and how they felt during the day when they answered the questionnaire. General self-efficacy can be described as a stable expectation of a person that "...expresses a subjective belief that they can cope with demanding requirements through their own actions.... Confidence in one's own abilities and skills should be understood as a stable personal resource for coping with stress" (Schwarzer 1993, 188–189). Unlike specific self-efficacy expectations (Bandura 1997), general self-efficacy expectations are understood as the sum of several self-efficacy expectations in different areas. Schwarzer (1993) assumes that general self-efficacy expectations can be a personal protective factor.

While self-efficacy can be considered a relatively persistent characteristic of a person, affective responses, depending on the method of questioning, may reflect the current or more distant effects of living conditions. Based on studies in different cultures, Watson, Clark and Tellegen (1988) concluded that affective structure is predominantly formed by two dimensions—positive affect (PA) and negative affect (NA). In their concept however, PA and NA express the characteristics of a person that correspond to positive and negative emotionality, expressing "individual differences in positive and negative emotional reactivity" (ibid., 1063). The authors assess both dimensions using 20 items from two PANAS scales with questions regarding the intensity of experience. This survey format relates more to a person's temperamental characteristics which are related to extraversion or neuroticism. Given that this, in addition to the scope of PA, are less suitable for the purposes of the planned research, a shorter PA alternative was chosen. This has 5 items in its original version (Džuka and Dalbert 2002). At the same time, positive affect was interpreted in accordance with the homeostatically protected mood hypothesis (Capic, Li and Cummins 2018). This explains why people usually feel positive, which is related to the assumption of the existence and functioning of so-called set-points "...set-points account for the normal positivity of SWB while its stability is accounted for by homeostatic processes." (ibid., 1). Capic, Li and Cummins (2018) expanded this assumption to say that it is homeostasis that protects and maintains a "homeostatically protected mood (HPMood)" at positive values. The emotional responses with which people react to the realities of life are short-lived and result in short-term deviations from the set point. As a result of homeostasis however, these deviations are repeatedly returned to the set point. Capic, Li and Cummins (2018, 3) state that long-term changes in positive experiences may also occur. These changes "...represent a persistent defeat of homeostasis due to the continued presence of a powerful stressor, such as may be generated by unemployment, persecution, pain, etc." Although the respondents living in western Ukraine are not directly affected by this strong stressor in this study, it

can be assumed that the conflict in the eastern part of the country threatens their affective system.

2.4 Proposed research model

The aim of the research was to determine the life satisfaction of residents in two self-governing regions in Slovakia bordering Ukraine as well as the residents of the Transcarpathian region in Ukraine. In order to address the objective of our research, life satisfaction was measured using an index in which overall satisfaction (OVERALLSAT) was an aggregate of four areas of life: Satisfaction with the economic situation (ECON), Satisfaction with the state of the environment (ENVIRON), Satisfaction with relationships between people in the region (RELAT) and Satisfaction with how local authority offices work in the city/municipality (LOCALGOV). In addition to checking gender, age, and education, general self-efficacy and how people felt on the day of the survey (PA) were also surveyed. Overall, the aim was to better understand people's satisfaction with life in Ukraine and to use the relational context of life satisfaction among Slovak residents for comparison purposes. While there was no hypothesis formulated regarding the differences between Ukrainians and Slovaks, two hypotheses were formulated concerning the personal characteristics examined that could influence life satisfaction:

1. It was assumed that general self-efficacy would facilitate coping with problems and promote life satisfaction, and that its effect would be significantly positive in relation to overall life satisfaction among residents in both countries.
2. Regarding the relationship of positive affect as a moderator influencing the relationship between country affiliation and overall life satisfaction, it was assumed that positive affect, would have a positive effect as a moderating factor in both countries. This is believed to be the result of the homeostatically protected mood mechanism. A worsening effect because of persistent defeat of homeostasis due to the continued presence of a powerful stressor was not predicted for residents of either country. The moderating (not mediating) effect of PA on the relationship between the two variables was preferred because it is not a matter of temporal sequence of variables, but of a plausible simultaneous reinforcing or weakening the effect on life satisfaction. As has been noted, "whereas mediation analysis focuses on how a causal effect operates, moderation analysis is used to address, when, or under what circumstances, or for what types of people that effect exists or does not and in what magnitude" (Hayes and Rockwood 2017, 47). Therefore, in accordance with the HPMood hypothesis, PA is shown as a moderator in the model (Figure 1) and should positively influence the relationship between affiliation with the country and life satisfaction.

FIGURE 1: PATH MODEL UNDER CONSIDERATION

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Measurement

The electronically administered questionnaire consisted of two parts. The first part included questions regarding demographic characteristics: gender, age, and education (primary education, secondary without A-Levels, secondary with A-Levels and university). In the second part of the questionnaire, there were questions representing the three assessed constructs. Due to space reasons the English version of the questionnaire, as well as the Slovak and Ukrainian versions are available upon request from the authors.

Life satisfaction was measured using twelve items from the life satisfaction index in the self-governing regions of Slovakia bordering Ukraine. The index was preferred over the scale as it was assumed that satisfaction with different areas of life does not have a single common cause but rather generates a common effect (for the difference and need to distinguish between the scale and the index, see MacKenzie and Podsakoff 2005). Due to the scope of the work described elsewhere (Lačný and Džuka 2025), only basic information will be outlined here. The twelve items in the questionnaire represent four areas of satisfaction: satisfaction with the economic situation, satisfaction with the state of the environment, satisfaction with relationships between people in the region, and satisfaction with how local authority offices work in the city/municipality. Each area is represented by three items that have reflective scale properties. For each item, the participants indicated their agreement on an 11-point scale ranging from 0 = no satisfaction to 10 = complete satisfaction. To obtain an overall score, the values of the individual domains representing lower-order constructs (LOC) were aggregated to form a higher-order construct (HOC). Such a measurement model is considered a reflective-formative higher-order construct (HOC, Type II) where the domains (lower-order constructs, LOC) are reflective and the total score is formative (cf. DeVellis and Thorpe 2021; Becker, Cheah, Gholamzade, Ringle and Sarstedt 2023).

General self-efficacy expectations (Schwarzer and Jerusalem 1999, 16) were assessed using ten items. For each item, the participants indicated their

agreement on an eleven-point scale ranging from not true at all to completely true.

Positive affect (PA) was measured using five items adapted from the original five-item SEHP scale (Džuka and Dalbert 2002). The participants expressed how they felt on the day of the study using five descriptive words (I am in a good mood, I am satisfied, I am happy, I experience joy, and I am excited) and expressed their agreement on an 11-point scale. This ranged from not true at all to completely true.

The Slovak versions of the instruments, including the demographic questions, were translated into Ukrainian. In accordance with good translation practice (see Brislin 1980), two bilingual translators familiar with the research were involved in the translation. One of them did the translation forward and the other back into the original language without seeing the original text.

3.2 Data and procedure

The data were collected through an agency. The respondents (N = 245 from Slovakia and N = 267 from Ukraine) had online access to the questionnaire through the agency's email. The sample selection ensured proportional representation of people from the two self-governing regions in Slovakia bordering Ukraine - the Prešov Self-Governing Region (793,182 inhabitants) and the Košice Self-Governing Region (767,685 inhabitants) as well as from the Transcarpathian Region (1,244,476 inhabitants, data from before 2022) in Ukraine.

TABLE 1: SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS (N = 512)

	Slovakia		Ukraine	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Persons	245	48	267	52
Gender				
Women	142	58	148	55
Men	103	42	119	45
Age				
18 - 29	51	21	55	21
30 - 39	56	23	54	20
40 - 49	59	24	57	21
50 - 59	45	18	55	21
60 and over	34	14	46	17
Education				
Primary	14	6	25	9
Secondary without A-Levels	50	20	45	17
Secondary with A-Levels	113	46	59	22
University	68	28	138	52
Type of economic activity				
Student	14	6	19	7
Permanent employment	143	58	108	40
Unemployed	24	10	43	16
Self-employed	18	7	36	14
Pensioner	37	15	42	16
Other	9	4	19	7

In addition to the proportional representation of the population from both countries, a quota selection was applied in relation to age. People from five age categories (18–29, 30–39, 40–49, 50–59, and 60 and over) were proportionally represented. There were no quotas used to select people based on their education or type of economic activity, although approximate ratios in relation to the size of their place of residence were considered. The data collection took

place in both countries simultaneously from 18 November to 10 December 2024. The sociodemographic characteristics of respondents from both countries are shown in Table 1.

3.3 Analytical approach

The data analysis was performed in two steps. Firstly, a descriptive analysis of all the variables was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 29. In the second step, an analysis of the complex relationships in the conceptual model was carried out using PLS-SEM. The choice of analysis was based on the research objective which was to assess the PLS path model's explanatory variables power. This is in line with the recommendations posed by Hair, Hult, Ringle and Sarstedt (2022, 31) who claim that in case the main goal of the research is to predict and explain the target constructs, PLS-SEM should be preferred. SmartPLS 4 software was used for the statistical analysis (Ringle, Wende and Becker 2024).

4 RESULTS

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics. The average scores for all the variables surveyed are higher in favour of Ukraine, except for PA (positive affect).

TABLE 2: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Variables	Slovakia		Ukraine	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Age	43.0	14.52	43.3	14.88
PA	5.95	2.12	5.62	2.29
SELFEFF	5.80	1.88	6.08	1.95
ECON	4.84	2.14	5.53	2.15
ENVIRON	6.05	2.22	6.80	2.27
RELAT	5.03	2.13	5.94	2.28
LOCALGOV	4.59	2.32	4.72	2.39
OVERALLSAT	20.45	6.66	22.94	7.31

Note: *M* and *SD* are used to represent the mean and standard deviation, respectively. PA – Positive affect, SELFEFF – general self-efficacy, ECON - Satisfaction with the economic situation, ENVIRON – Satisfaction with the state of the environment, RELAT – Satisfaction with relationships between people in the region, LOCALGOV – Satisfaction with how local authority offices work in the city/municipality, OVERALLSAT – Overall life satisfaction.

Table 3 shows the results of the evaluation of measurement models in terms of the loading indicators, reliability and convergent validity (AVE) for all the latent variables.

TABLE 3: ASSESSMENT OF INTERNAL CONSISTENCY RELIABILITY AND CONVERGENT VALIDITY (AVE) OF THE SCALES

Scala/Items	Loading	Cronbach's alpha	rhoA	rhoC	AVE
PA		0.911	0.921	0.933	0.736
Good Mood1	0.850				
Satisfied2	0.866				
Happy3	0.882				
Joy4	0.890				
Excited5	0.798				
ECON		0.785	0.785	0.875	0.700
Econ1	0.854				
Econ2	0.805				
Econ3	0.850				
ENVIRON		0.859	0.885	0.913	0.779
Environ1	0.912				
Environ2	0.854				
Environ3	0.881				
RELAT		0.922	0.922	0.950	0.864
Relat1	0.917				
Relat2	0.943				
Relat3	0.928				
LOCALGOV		0.914	0.928	0.946	0.853
Localgov1	0.944				
Localgov2	0.936				
Localgov3	0.889				
SELFEFF		0.944	0.953	0.953	0.673
Selfefficacy1	0.522				
Selfefficacy2	0.791				
Selfefficacy3	0.811				
Selfefficacy4	0.829				
Selfefficacy5	0.861				
Selfefficacy6	0.863				
Selfefficacy7	0.873				
Selfefficacy8	0.864				
Selfefficacy9	0.861				
Selfefficacy10	0.868				

Note: See Table 2.

The results (Table 3) show that all the reflectively measured constructs (PA, self-efficacy, ECON, ENVIRON, RELAT and LOCALGOV as LOC (low order constructs)) are reliable and valid. There was only one loading of the SELFEFF (Selfefficacy1) which did not exceed the threshold value of 0.708. The average variance extracted (AVE) was higher than the critical value of 0.5, and all the construct reliabilities i.e. Cronbach's alpha, the coefficients rhoA, and the composite reliability rhoC had values above 0.7 (Sarstedt, Hair, Pick, Liengaad, Radomir and Ringle 2022).

The discriminant validity assessment, based on the heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) ratio of the correlations measure (Henseler, Ringle and Sarstedt 2015) showed that all the HTMT values were significantly lower than 0.85. This supports the discriminant validity of the measures (Table 4). "Discriminant validity ensures that a construct measure is empirically unique and represents phenomena of interest that other measures in a structural equation model do not capture (Hair et al. 2010)." (ibid., 116). The discriminant validity values of all measures in the tested structural model met the required criteria. This means that each construct is empirically unique and captures a phenomenon that other constructs in the PLS path model do not represent (Franke and Sarstedt 2019).

TABLE 4: ASSESSMENT OF DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY USING THE HETERO TRAIT-MONOTRAIT RATIO OF CORRELATIONS CRITERION

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. ECON	-					
2. ENVIRON	0.414	-				
3. LOCALGOV	0.591	0.470	-			
4. RELAT	0.617	0.535	0.648	-		
5. PA	0.567	0.296	0.355	0.434	-	
6. SELFEFF	0.450	0.364	0.311	0.379	0.514	-
7. PAxCOUNTRY	0.416	0.194	0.271	0.319	0.784	0.342

4.3 Structural equation modelling analysis

4.3.1 Collinearity

The structural model was firstly assessed for collinearity issues by examining the variance inflation factor (VIF) values of all the predictor constructs in the model. Table 5 shows the VIF values of all predictors in the model. All values were less than 3 which indicates that collinearity was not a problem.

4.3.2 Assessment of the higher-order model with moderation

As recommended by Becker et al. (2023), the disjoint two-stage approach was used. In the first stage, the disjoint two-stage approach only draws on the LOCs and connects them to all constructs in the model which are antecedents and consequences of the higher-order construct. It should only continue with the second stage if the LOCs meet the measurement model evaluation criteria. As can be seen in Table 3, all LOC met the criteria. The second stage of the disjoint two-stage approach uses the latent variable scores from Stage 1 as the HOC indicators, and all the other (non-hierarchical) constructs are measured with their original indicators (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2: TESTED MODEL AND ESTIMATION IN THE SECOND STAGE. BOOTSTRAP T-STATISTICS BASED ON 10,000 REPLICATIONS

One global item was used as an alternative measure of the higher-order construct as a criterion in the redundancy analysis: “How satisfied are you overall with your life in the area where you live?” The path coefficient value of 0.688 can be considered close to the threshold value of 0.7.

4.3.3 Significance and relevance of the path coefficients (standardized regression coefficients)

TABLE 5: ASSESSMENT OF THE MODEL BASED ON THE RESULTS OF THE SECOND STAGE OF THE DISJUNCTIVE TWO-STAGE APPROACH (BECKER ET AL. 2023)

Relationship	Std beta	p	2.5%	97.5%	VIF	f ²	R ²
COUNTRY→ OVERALLSAT	.448	.000	.297	.589	1.031	.08	.380
SELFEFF→ OVERALLSAT	.222	.000	.129	.308	1.345	.06	
Gender → OVERALLSAT	-.118	.146	-.276	.043	1.097	.01	
Age → OVERALLSAT	.035	.347	-.036	.112	1.129	.00	
Education → OVERALLSAT	.083	.044	.004	.165	1.119	.00	
PA→OVERALLSAT	.404	.000	.291	.512	2.708	.10	
PAxCOUNTRY→ OVERALLSAT	.032	.679	-.121	.179	2.388	.00	

Note: COUNTRY, 0 = Slovakia, 1 = Ukraine. Gender, 0 = male, 1 = female. Education, 1 = Primary, 2 = Secondary without A-Levels, 3 = Secondary with A-Levels, 4 = University. Ratings of SELFEFF, PA and OVERALLSAT range from 0 to 10, higher value indicates stronger endorsement of the construct

Table 5 shows the results of the analyses of the tested model. The HOC measurement model (OVERALLSAT) was assessed along with all other measurement models and the structural model by applying the usual evaluation criteria for PLS-SEM. The R-square value indicates that 38% of the variance was explained by the model. A (non-parametric) percentile bootstrapping method with 10,000 subsamples was used to test the significance of the tested variables. The results have revealed that four path coefficients of the seven tested life satisfaction factors were significant (Table 5). The only exceptions to this were age (0.035, $p > 0.10$) and gender (-0.118, $p > 0.10$). The effects of country 0.448 ($p < 0.01$), two personal factors, self-efficacy 0.222 ($p < 0.01$) and the direct effect of positive affect 0.404 ($p < 0.01$) were found to be highly significant. Education was found to be marginally significant (0.083, $p < 0.05$). With regards to the tested moderation of PA, the effect was not significant (0.032, $p > 0.10$). The confidence interval values confirm the significance of the effects. Table 5 also shows the effect size coefficients f^2 . Values f^2 from 0.02/0.15/0.35 can be considered weak/medium/strong effect sizes (Chin 2010). The direct effect of PA is close to a medium effect size, country and self-efficacy also reach values greater than a small effect while education has zero effect.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The results show a somewhat surprising difference between the inhabitants of Slovakia and Ukraine with those in the Transcarpathian region of Ukraine showing a significantly higher score in terms of overall life satisfaction. Both general self-efficacy and positive affect contributed significantly to 38% of the explained variance in life satisfaction among residents of both countries. The influence of gender and age was found to be insignificant and the effect of education marginal. The moderating relationship of PA as a possible additional factor influencing the relationship between country and overall life satisfaction was shown to be insignificant. In other words, the influence of the positive experiences of the inhabitants in both countries was about the same and did not influence life satisfaction in a specific way beyond the identified main effect.

Land and Michalos (2018) have highlighted the frequent research into the relationship between demographic factors and life satisfaction in the context of quality-of-life assessment and the neglect of personal characteristics. While the tested model verified the influence of three specific demographic factors (gender, age and education), their contribution to the overall life satisfaction of residents

in Ukraine and Slovakia was insignificant after taking personal factors into account. On the contrary, general self-efficacy (how well the respondents are equipped to cope with the demands of life) and how they feel emotionally on the day of the survey were confirmed as being significant and efficient factors of overall life satisfaction for those in both countries. As noted by Ferguson (2009), R-squared greater than 25% in the case of social science data is considered a moderate effect. While the 38% found in the research can be considered as such, it is not close to 64% which is the value of a strong effect. It can be assumed that there are additional factors of life satisfaction that were not considered in this research.

A direct and positive influence of general self-efficacy was confirmed and in line with expectations. The insignificant moderating relationship between positive affect and differences between countries in overall life satisfaction is consistent with the theory of homeostatically protected mood (Capic et al. 2018). Although a deterioration in positive experiences could be expected among the population in Ukraine due to less favourable economic and environmental living conditions and a lower degree of autonomy of Ukrainian local and regional governments, the interaction between positive affect and country (moderating effect) was insignificant. This can be interpreted in the sense that the levels of positive affect among the populations of both countries were about the same. In other words, the homeostatic mechanism of positive affect remained at a comparable level and was not burdened to such an extent among those in Ukraine that its beneficial effect on the assessment of overall life satisfaction was weakened. This means that homeostatic processes maintained positive affect at favourable levels thanks to the individual set point. While this protective function may fail under stressful circumstances, it did not threaten the respondents in either country to such an extent that this effect would manifest itself (compare Capic et al. 2018).

It is necessary to interpret the result in terms of what caused the lower score among Slovak residents, who live in a more favourable economic and environmental reality and in a decentralized form of public administration. The two self-governing regions studied are in the eastern part of Slovakia which is relatively less developed than other parts of the country. Indeed, the Slovak-Ukrainian borderlands includes regions with lower per capita GDP in comparison to more developed regions in Slovakia. In addition to high unemployment, average incomes below national income levels, is another factor contributing to the lower level of purchasing power in eastern Slovak regions. While the current research compared residents in two different countries, the residents in eastern Slovakia do not subjectively compare themselves with residents of Ukraine in terms of satisfaction with the areas of life surveyed, but rather with groups of residents in their own country. The context for assessing their own situation could be represented by the more prosperous regions of Slovakia, especially the western part of the country, with which the inhabitants of the east tend to compare themselves. As such, this may have influenced the less favourable assessment of their own life satisfaction.

In a similar respect, it is important to consider the subjectively represented context of the assessment of satisfaction among residents in the Transcarpathian region where the conflict did not directly take place. The relational framework of the inhabitants in this part of the country may provide a sense of privilege and influence their responses in their subjective assessment of life satisfaction. If the social relational framework was behind the differences, then it would seem appropriate to take in future research social representations into account.

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ZADOVOLJSTVO Z ŽIVLJENJEM MED PREBIVALCI SLOVAŠKO-UKRAJINSKEGA OBMEJNEGA OBMOČJA

Cilj raziskave je bil oceniti, kako zadovoljni so prebivalci obmejnih regij s pomembnimi področji svojega življenja. V študiji, ki primerja zadovoljstvo z življenjem med prebivalci zahodnega dela Ukrajine (N = 267) in prebivalci vzhodne Slovaške (N = 245), so bile individualne značilnosti, samoučinkovitost in pozitivni afekt interpretirani v skladu s hipotezo homeostatsko zaščitenega razpoloženja. Zadovoljstvo z življenjem je bilo merjeno z indeksom, hibridnim reflektivno-formativnim konstruktom, ki združuje štiri pomembna področja. Učinek običajno obravnavanih demografskih značilnosti je bil kontroliran, medtem ko je bil preizkušen vpliv dveh osebnostnih značilnosti: splošne samoučinkovitosti kot neposrednega dejavnika in pozitivnega afekta kot moderatorja zadovoljstva z življenjem. Rezultati kažejo višjo raven zadovoljstva z življenjem med ukrajinskimi prebivalci, pri čemer se moderatorski učinek ni izkazal za statistično pomembnega.

Ključne besede: indeks; zadovoljstvo z življenjem; Slovaška; Ukrajina; obmejno območje; HPMood; PLS-SEM.